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Bridging the Energy Gap in ASEAN: Scaling Green Finance and Carbon Markets for a Sustainable Transition

 Ohn Zin Lin¹

¹Department of Applied Electronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Moravian-Silesian, Czech Republic | ²School of Electrical Engineering & Center of Excellence of Sustainable Energy and Climate Change, Telkom University, Bandung, Indonesia

Correspondence: Ohn Zin Lin (ohn.zin.lin@vsb.cz)

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ABSTRACT

Fragmented regulations, limited access to green finance, and underdeveloped carbon markets impede ASEAN's clean energy transition. This paper assesses global best practices, including the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), and green bond standards, through comparative policy analysis, evaluating their suitability for ASEAN's context. By examining specific national cases from Indonesia, Singapore, and Thailand, we identify critical opportunities for enhancing institutional capacities, harmonizing regulatory frameworks, and scaling climate-aligned investment. A strategic roadmap is developed, focusing particularly on carbon pricing mechanisms, blended finance solutions, and digital innovations such as blockchain and artificial intelligence for regional energy market integration. Findings underline the necessity of coordinated regional carbon markets, standardized green finance instruments, and digitally driven transparency tools. This integrated approach offers ASEAN a pragmatic pathway to accelerate its low-carbon transition, ensuring both economic resilience and regional cooperation. Future research is recommended to explore socioeconomic impacts on vulnerable sectors and strategies for operationalizing regional carbon pricing across ASEAN's diverse political economies.

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1 | Introduction

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) faces an urgent energy challenge as rapid economic growth drives a surge in energy demand (Chien et al. 2023). Despite increasing commitments to sustainability, fossil fuels such as particularly coal and natural gas continue to dominate the region's energy mix. This reliance on carbon-intensive energy sources raises environmental concerns and poses significant obstacles to meeting global climate commitments, including those outlined in the Paris Agreement (Energy (ACE) 2023). Recognizing the need

to curb greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, ASEAN countries have pledged to transition toward renewable energy, yet financial constraints remain a critical barrier to achieving this goal (Sasaki et al. 2025; Vakulchuk et al. 2023).

To overcome these barriers, financial innovations including green bonds and carbon credits are increasingly leveraged to draw private capital and support decarbonization efforts (ADB 2022; Shobande et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2024). The European Union (EU) has successfully implemented advanced models for green finance and carbon markets, offering

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valuable insights that could be adapted to the ASEAN context (Bertoldi et al. 2021; Fatica and Panzica 2020; Sitarz et al. 2024). Notably, the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), introduced in 2021, is being implemented in phases from 2023 to 2026 to mitigate carbon leakage and ensure a level playing field for emissions-intensive and trade-exposed (EITE) industries. By imposing a carbon cost on certain imports including aluminum, cement, fertilizers, iron, steel, and electricity, CBAM aligns with the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) and reinforces carbon pricing mechanisms (Beaufils et al. 2023; Dobranschi et al. 2024; Korpar et al. 2023; Perdana and Vielle 2022). However, its implementation has raised concerns over global trade compliance, economic impacts on developing countries, and sectoral adaptation. Additionally, leading Asian economies including Singapore, Indonesia, and Thailand have pioneered carbon pricing strategies, voluntary carbon markets, and Green Sukuk financing, demonstrating successful localized approaches. By analyzing market structures, financial instruments, and regulatory frameworks, this study assesses how ASEAN can adapt these mechanisms to attract private-sector investment, harmonize policy frameworks, and scale up renewable energy deployment.

While previous studies have explored green financing and carbon markets, limited research has assessed how these mechanisms can be effectively adapted to ASEAN's unique economic and regulatory landscape. This study contributes to the literature by conducting a comparative analysis of global and ASEAN green finance models, identifying key adaptation strategies for ASEAN's renewable energy transition. Furthermore, it provides policy recommendations to enhance green bond frameworks and strengthen regional carbon market mechanisms.

Figure 1 illustrates the various scenarios forecasting the proportion of renewable energy within the Total Primary Energy Supply (TPES) between 2022 and 2050. The region has set a 23% renewable energy target by 2025 (Energy (ACE) 2023). The Baseline Scenario (BAS) does not meet the 23% target by 2025. The Accelerated Transition Scenario (ATS) scenario reaches

23% only after 2025, showing gradual progress. The Rapid Advancement Scenario (RAS) and Carbon Neutral Scenario (CNS) show significant RE growth, with CNS reaching a majority share of RE by mid-century. The CNS scenario aligns with a strong decarbonization pathway, while RAS and ATS provide intermediate pathways. This figure highlights the necessity of strong policy measures to achieve renewable energy targets and long-term sustainability goals.

This paper explores the role of green bonds, carbon credits, and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) in accelerating renewable energy development in ASEAN. It draws lessons from the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) and other global best practices to assess the feasibility of scaling up green finance and carbon markets in the region.

Despite progress in individual ASEAN markets, the regional landscape remains fragmented, with varying levels of carbon pricing adoption, green bond issuance, and renewable energy financing mechanisms. By comparing ASEAN's progress with the EU, US, and Asia-Pacific market leaders, this paper aims to:

- Identify key financial and policy challenges in ASEAN's clean energy transition.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of green finance tools such as green bonds, sustainability-linked bonds (SLBs), voluntary carbon markets, and blended finance.
- Propose a structured policy roadmap for enhancing carbon market development, regional cooperation, and private-sector engagement.

It is hypothesized that adapting global best practices such as the EU ETS, CBAM, and green bonds can support the development of a harmonized, investment-ready framework for ASEAN's clean energy transition. Through this comparative analysis, the research contributes strategic insights for policymakers, investors, and international partners seeking to mobilize capital for ASEAN's renewable energy transition. It underscores the importance of harmonized policy frameworks, innovative

FIGURE 1 | Renewable energy scenarios in ASEAN (Data Source: Energy (ACE) 2023).

financial instruments, and digital-driven transparency solutions to ensure a resilient, sustainable, and low-carbon future for ASEAN. We focus on Indonesia, Singapore, and Thailand because they combine policy maturity, data availability, and instrument diversity that are relevant to ASEAN transferability, as detailed in Section 4.

2 | Literature Review Methodology

We conducted a PRISMA-informed review (Figure 2) focusing on ASEAN green finance and carbon market mechanisms, including financial instruments, carbon pricing and trading systems (ETS, offsets, and MRV), standards and taxonomies, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), and digital transparency tools. Searches covered Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and ScienceDirect, as well as key institutional repositories such as ACE, IEA, World Bank, ADB, IMF, UNFCCC, and ICAP for the period from 2015 to September 2025.

Search queries combined instrument, market, and ASEAN country terms (Table 1). After removing duplicates and low-quality records, 107 studies met the inclusion criteria, which included peer-reviewed papers and institutional reports containing data, methods, or policy analyses relevant to ASEAN or clearly transferable global lessons. Excluded records included opinion papers without analysis, technology-only studies without a finance or policy component, and research unrelated to the ASEAN region.

Data were organized by instrument type, jurisdiction, design parameters, outcomes, and metrics, and safeguard mechanisms. Because the studies used diverse methods and metrics,

we applied a narrative comparative synthesis instead of a meta-analysis. Three focal cases were selected for their policy maturity and variety of instruments: Indonesia (sovereign green sukuk and Islamic finance), Singapore (carbon tax and trading hub), and Thailand (T-VER, renewable auctions, and MRV).

3 | Green Finance and Carbon Markets in ASEAN: Progress and Challenges

This section examines the current state of green finance and carbon markets in ASEAN and presents a comparative overview of key policies across member states.

3.1 | The Energy Gap and Renewable Energy Development in ASEAN

The energy gap in ASEAN is driven by the region's rapid economic growth and its heavy reliance on fossil fuel (Energy (ACE) 2023). The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates that energy demand in the region could surge by 60% by 2040 (Agency (IEA) 2019; Aleluia et al. 2022). This rising demand, coupled with a dependence on coal and natural gas, has made it difficult for the region to transition to cleaner energy sources. While renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydropower offer considerable potential to meet ASEAN's energy needs, their adoption has been slow due to various challenges (Agency (IEA) 2019; Li, Nian, et al. 2020). Bioenergy is also a material pillar of ASEAN decarbonization, but its scale-up hinges on logistics (residue aggregation, quality standards, traceability) and coherent policy coordination across the region (Balanay and Halog 2024).

FIGURE 2 | PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of study selection.

TABLE 1 | Search-query structure used for literature identification.

Focus area	Example search string
Green finance instruments	("green bond" OR "sustainability-linked bond" OR "sukuk" OR "blended finance" OR "de-risking" OR "reverse auction") AND (ASEAN OR Indonesia OR Singapore OR Thailand OR Viet* OR Malaysia OR Philippines OR Cambodia OR Laos OR Myanmar OR Brunei)
Carbon pricing and markets	("carbon tax" OR "emissions trading system" OR ETS OR "offset market" OR "voluntary carbon" OR "MRV" OR "Article 6") AND (ASEAN ... country names)
Trade and CBAM	(CBAM OR "border adjustment" OR "carbon leakage") AND (ASEAN ... country names)
Standards and taxonomy	("green taxonomy" OR "EU taxonomy" OR "ICMA" OR "ASEAN taxonomy") AND (finance OR investment)
Digital transparency	(blockchain OR "digital MRV" OR "registry" OR "traceability") AND (carbon market OR credits OR offsets)

As one of the primary barriers, high upfront capital costs deter renewable energy investment in ASEAN, especially where domestic finance is limited (Wahyudi and Palupi 2023). Meeting the 23% RE in TPES by 2025 target requires about USD 27 billion per year, yet only USD 8 billion was mobilized during 2016–2021, underscoring the funding gap (Vakulchuk et al. 2023). This disparity underscores the financial hurdles that impede the transition to renewable energy.

Inconsistent policies and regulatory frameworks across ASEAN create uncertainty for investors (Vakulchuk et al. 2023). Policies that restrict foreign participation further limit access to international capital (Damu et al. 2023). Outdated and conflicting rules that do not reflect renewable project requirements make markets difficult to navigate (Oduro et al. 2024).

First, regulatory gaps impede effective RE market design in ASEAN. Many countries lack comprehensive policies for grid integration, slowing progress toward the 23% RE by 2025 APAEC target due to inefficiencies and unclear guidance for private investors (Damu et al. 2023; Vakulchuk et al. 2023). The absence of a conducive regulatory environment discourages investment, as potential investors face uncertainty regarding the viability and

profitability of renewable energy projects (Fahim et al. 2023). Second, inadequate grid and logistics infrastructure raise project risk and slow renewable deployment across ASEAN. Stronger logistical performance is associated with better economic outcomes for RE initiatives (Khan et al. 2021). Weak transmission, interconnections, and enabling infrastructure hinder integration and deter private capital (Nam and Burke 2022; Vakulchuk et al. 2023).

The overall market design and integration of electricity trade within ASEAN are crucial for attracting private capital. A multilateral electricity market, as envisaged in APAEC, could enable cross-border trade and strengthen competition, improving bankability (Li, Rakhmah, and Wada 2020). However, reliance on bilateral deals and fragmented market rules limits regional integration and deters private capital (Nam and Burke 2022). Therefore, the challenge of attracting private capital for renewable energy development in ASEAN countries is significantly hindered by the lack of robust market structures. Despite ASEAN's renewable energy potential, financing and policy fragmentation remain major hurdles. Global best practices demonstrate that harmonized policy frameworks and strategic financial instruments such as the EU Green Bond Standard, blended finance programs, and sector-based ETS pilots can accelerate private investment and enhance market confidence. As ASEAN works toward a unified carbon pricing strategy, countries can adopt progressive models such as Singapore's carbon tax trajectory and Thailand's voluntary carbon market framework to build a more resilient green finance ecosystem.

The previous study identified three main obstacles to renewable energy growth in ASEAN: financial, policy and regulatory, and market readiness barriers. These obstacles are exacerbated by several interrelated factors including limited financial instruments, low bankability, insufficient grid infrastructure, inconsistent policies, and a lack of competitive electricity markets. Addressing these challenges requires a structured approach that integrates financial de-risking, harmonized regulatory frameworks, and private-sector participation. As demonstrated by global best practices, countries that have successfully scaled renewable energy investments have relied on three key drivers:

- Innovative green finance instruments (e.g., green bonds, sustainability-linked bonds, and blended finance).
- Effective carbon pricing mechanisms (e.g., sectoral ETS pilots, carbon tax policies, and voluntary carbon markets).
- Supportive policy frameworks that reduce investor uncertainty and enhance market participation.

To bridge ASEAN's energy financing gap, the following sections examine how green finance instruments and carbon markets can accelerate investment in clean energy.

3.2 | Overview of ASEAN Green Finance and Carbon Markets

According to the survey of Asia Development Bank, the green bond market in ASEAN has demonstrated strong growth potential and shows promising signs of further expansion. In the

region, countries such as Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines, and Singapore have taken early steps in issuing green bonds to fund renewable energy and other green infrastructure projects (Bank (ADB) and Institute (GGGI) 2022). Furthermore, in Indonesia, transparent carbon-emission disclosure has emerged as an important lever for enhancing corporate value. As firms increase transparency to align with international standards, they report higher valuation and stronger investor confidence. Consequently, credible carbon-credit markets and robust disclosure can attract private capital for low-carbon projects (Wibowo et al. 2023).

These bonds have helped tap into a growing pool of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)-focused investors, particularly those looking for sustainable investment opportunities. However, despite some success, the volume of green bond issuances in ASEAN remains relatively low compared to developed markets. Several factors contribute to this (Bank (ADB) and Institute (GGGI) 2022):

- *Lack of standardization*: The absence of harmonized green bond standards across ASEAN makes it difficult for issuers and investors to navigate the market.
- *Low awareness*: Many local investors and financial institutions are not familiar with the green bond market or its potential for long-term returns.
- *High costs*: Certification, monitoring, and reporting requirements for green bonds can increase the cost of issuance, which may deter smaller issuers.

Carbon credits, which allow companies to offset their emissions by purchasing credits tied to emission-reducing projects, are becoming an important financial tool for achieving carbon neutrality. Carbon credits can be traded in either voluntary or compliance markets, providing flexibility for businesses looking to reduce their carbon footprint (Agency (IEA) and GenZero 2024). However, carbon markets in ASEAN are still in their early stages, with only a few countries like Singapore having implemented carbon pricing mechanisms (Li et al. 2023; Li and Su 2017). Other nations, such as Thailand, Vietnam, and Indonesia, are exploring the possibility of establishing carbon markets, especially in sectors such as forestry and energy (Bunjongsiri 2019; Do and Burke 2021; Purnamasari and Nurachmah 2023). ASEAN's vast natural resources, including forests that can serve as major carbon sinks, present an opportunity for developing carbon credit projects, particularly through nature-based solutions (NBS). Nonetheless, the carbon markets face several challenges (Agency and London 2023):

- *Low carbon prices*: Carbon prices in existing ASEAN markets tend to be too low to incentivize significant emissions reductions.
- *Weak regulatory frameworks*: Limited regulations and lack of enforcement hinder the development of robust carbon markets in the region.
- *Investor uncertainty*: The fragmented market structures and lack of standardization create uncertainty for investors interested in carbon credits.

The ASEAN region has made notable progress in green finance, and countries such as Indonesia, Singapore, and Malaysia are leading on green-bond issuance and carbon-market initiatives. In particular, Indonesia pioneered sovereign green sukuk, thereby mobilizing funds for renewable-energy projects; meanwhile, Malaysia followed with its own green sukuk framework (Hendra et al. 2023; Ramadhan 2020). Singapore has taken a different approach, integrating sovereign green bonds with its Singapore Green Plan 2030, aimed at sustainable infrastructure investments (Singapore 2022). Despite these advancements, the uptake of green bonds in ASEAN remains uneven. Key barriers include high issuance costs, complex certification requirements, and inconsistent regulatory frameworks across countries (Deschryver and Mariz 2020; Saravade and Weber 2020). While Singapore and Malaysia have matured green bond markets, other ASEAN nations are still in the early stages of policy development and investor engagement (Primambudi 2023). Encouraging regional collaboration, private-sector participation, and policy standardization will be essential for strengthening ASEAN's green finance ecosystem (Azaki and Lutfi 2022; Kusmayadi and Koestoer 2022).

Table 2 provides an overview of ASEAN countries' progress in green finance and carbon market initiatives, highlighting key policies, financial instruments, and regulatory frameworks shaping the region's transition to a low-carbon economy. Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand lead in green finance, with Indonesia pioneering Green Sukuk, Malaysia implementing ASEAN Green Bond Standards, and Singapore issuing sovereign green bonds as part of its Green Plan 2030. Meanwhile, Vietnam and the Philippines have launched green bond frameworks and public-private climate finance initiatives to support clean energy investments.

However, Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar remain in the early stages, relying primarily on donor-funded renewable projects and REDD+ carbon offsets, with no established ETS or carbon tax mechanisms. In terms of carbon market development, Singapore is the most advanced, being the first ASEAN country to implement a carbon tax and establish a regional carbon trading hub (CIX). Indonesia and Malaysia have initiated carbon credit trading and voluntary carbon markets, while Vietnam and Thailand are developing national ETS frameworks. Despite this progress, challenges persist, including regulatory inconsistencies, low carbon prices, and limited investor participation. To accelerate green finance and carbon markets, ASEAN nations must harmonize policies, strengthen private-sector engagement, and expand carbon pricing mechanisms to create a more integrated and scalable low-carbon economy.

3.3 | Green Finance and Carbon Market Instruments

This subsection classifies the tools that ASEAN governments and markets are using to mobilize capital and to create credible price signals. Table 3 categorizes the instruments based on type while distinguishing between Green Finance and Carbon Market Instruments based on the preliminary review.

On the other hand, Carbon Market Instruments focus on pricing emissions and incentivizing reductions. Emissions Trading Systems (ETS) enable the trading of carbon allowances, while Carbon Credits (CC) and Carbon Offsets (CO) allow companies to either comply with regulations or voluntarily offset their emissions. Carbon Taxes (CT) directly impose costs on

emissions, whereas the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) acts as a trade regulation to prevent carbon leakage by aligning import prices with domestic carbon costs. The classification in Table 3 highlights the complementary roles of Green Finance in mobilizing sustainable investments and Carbon Market Instruments in regulating and mitigating emissions.

TABLE 2 | Overview of green finance and carbon market initiatives in ASEAN.

Country	Green finance initiatives	Carbon market initiatives
Indonesia	Green Sukuk (Ali et al. 2024), Sustainable Banking Regulations (Reform (IESR) 2022)	ETS Pilot for coal plants, Carbon Tax (delayed), REDD+ Credits (IDXCarbon 2024)
Malaysia	ASEAN Green Bond Standards (Forum (ACMF) 2018), Green Sukuk (Malaysia 2021), Green Technology Financing Scheme (GTFS) (Idris et al. 2024)	Voluntary Carbon Market (Berhad et al. 2023), ETS Planning (Alias et al. 2024)
Singapore	Sovereign Green Bond (Singapore 2022), Singapore Green Plan 2030 (Yeow 2022)	Carbon Tax (Yeow 2022), Carbon Trading Hub (CIX) (Quah and Tan 2022)
Thailand	Sustainability Bonds, SLBs (Public Debt Management Office (PDMO) 2024), Green Investment Incentives (OECD 2024)	Voluntary ETS, Carbon Credit Trading (Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Vietnam	Green Bond Framework (Nguyen et al. 2024), Renewable Energy Auctions (Azhgaliyeva and Mishra 2022)	Planned National ETS (Chu et al. 2023), Corporate Carbon Reporting (Khương et al. 2025)
Philippines	Green Bonds (Bank 2022; Dong et al. 2023), Public-Private Climate Finance (Navarro 2024)	Carbon Pricing (Group 2022), Forest Carbon Offsets (Republic of the Philippines and Resources 2021)
Cambodia	Early-Stage Frameworks (Cambodia and Cambodia 2022) Donor-Funded Renewable Projects (Bank (ADB) 2019)	REDD+ Credits (Nhem and Lee 2020), No ETS or Carbon Tax
Laos	Early-Stage Frameworks (Treanor et al. 2024), Donor-Funded Renewable Projects (Pillai 2014)	REDD+ Credits (Hiratsuka et al. 2022), No ETS or Carbon Tax
Myanmar	Not Available Donor-Funded Renewable Projects (Thema et al. 2020)	REDD+ Carbon Offsets (Programme 2015), No ETS or Carbon Tax

TABLE 3 | Main categories of green finance and carbon market instruments.

Category	Instrument	Type
Green finance instruments (Dogan et al. 2022; Erdogdu 2025; Niyazbekova et al. 2024)	Green bonds (GB)	Funds
	Green loans (GL)	Loans
	Sustainability-linked bonds (SLBs)	Performance-based
	Green equity funds (GEF)	Investment
	Environmental impact bonds (EIBs)	Impact-based
Carbon market instruments (Beaufils et al. 2023; Gilchrist et al. 2021; Verma et al. 2023)	Emissions trading systems (ETS)	Cap-and-trade
	Carbon credits (CC)	Tradable
	Carbon offsets (CO)	Offsetting
	Carbon taxes (CT)	Tax-based
	Carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM)	Trade regulation

Figure 3 illustrates the key differences between Carbon Market Instruments and Green Finance Instruments in terms of focus, mechanisms, examples, and target users. While Carbon Market Instruments aim to reduce emissions through pricing and trading mechanisms, Green Finance Instruments focus on funding sustainable projects through various financial tools. While carbon markets help put a price on emissions, green finance mobilizes capital for sustainable projects. Therefore, both play essential roles in climate action and low-carbon transition.

4 | Case Studies

4.1 | Successful Green Bond Issuance: Indonesia's Sovereign Green Sukuk

Green Sukuk marks a notable innovation in Islamic finance, designed to fund environmentally sustainable projects while adhering to Sharia principles. In 2018, Indonesia pioneered the world's first sovereign Green Sukuk, issuing USD 1.25 billion to finance climate-friendly projects (Fitrah and Soemitra 2022; Ministry of Finance 2024). By 2024, Indonesia had more than doubled its Sukuk issuance to USD 2.35 billion, demonstrating growing market confidence in Islamic green finance (Ministry of Finance 2024). This initiative not only highlights Indonesia's leadership in the green bond market but also sets a precedent for other ASEAN nations to adopt sustainable financing mechanisms.

According to Ali et al. (2024), the Shariah-compliant green sukuk operates through a simple sequence. First, a special purpose vehicle (SPV) issues the sukuk and channels the proceeds to eligible green projects. Second, investment agents manage the project portfolio. Third, project cash flows are returned to the SPV. Fourth, the SPV makes periodic distributions to sukuk holders as agreed. Finally, at maturity, the portfolio is redeemed according to pre-agreed terms, thereby linking the transparent use of proceeds to investor returns (Ali et al. 2024).

As a summary, the structure ensures that green project investments are financed in a Shariah-compliant manner.

FIGURE 3 | Key differences between carbon market instruments and green finance (illustrated by authors).

The proliferation of Green Sukuk is supported by increasing public and investor awareness of environmental sustainability. Investors are showing a strong preference for ethical financial products, thereby stimulating market expansion (Primambudi 2023). Islamic finance principles, which emphasize ethical funding and social responsibility, align naturally with the objectives of Green Sukuk, creating a synergistic green finance ecosystem in Indonesia (Teichmann et al. 2023).

Furthermore, the integration of Green Sukuk into Indonesia's financial landscape has been strategically driven by governmental and financial institutions. The Sustainable Finance Roadmap, launched by the Indonesian government, has been instrumental in embedding green finance into the broader economic framework (Kusmayadi and Koestoeer 2022). Additionally, initiatives such as the Indonesian Sustainable Finance Initiative (ISFI) reflect collaborative efforts aimed at promoting sustainable financing and enhancing the visibility of Green Sukuk (Sapiri and Putra 2023). A key consideration is the performance impact of Green Sukuk on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and corporate governance. Existing research highlights the necessity for Islamic banks and financial institutions to align their operations with sustainability objectives, thereby enhancing market positioning and contributing to community welfare (Widiastuti et al. 2022; Ye and Dela 2023).

Figure 4 illustrates the key milestones in Indonesia's Green Sukuk market development and its fund allocation to sustainable projects. Beginning with the establishment of the Green Bond & Sukuk Framework in 2017, Indonesia issued its first sovereign Green Sukuk in 2018 (USD 1.25 billion), marking a significant step in Islamic green finance. By 2024, the issuance had grown to USD 2.35 billion, including a 30-year Green Sukuk, reflecting increased market confidence. The funds raised have been allocated to renewable energy projects, climate-resilient infrastructure, and sustainable transportation, supporting Indonesia's net-zero and sustainable development goals.

While Indonesia has successfully positioned itself as a leader in Islamic green finance, challenges remain in scaling up Green Sukuk issuance beyond sovereign bonds. The market continues to be dominated by government issuances, with limited private-sector participation and weak integration with broader investment frameworks.

Key challenges in Green Sukuk development are:

- Limited corporate participation (Primambudi 2023; Ye and Dela 2023): Green Sukuk issuance is still dominated by the government, and corporate issuers remain scarce. Stronger incentives and supportive regulations are needed to encourage private offerings and diversify market players.
- Weak integration with private investments (Primambudi 2023; Widiastuti et al. 2022): Engagement with private investors and financial institutions is limited, constraining market liquidity. Greater collaboration with Islamic investment funds and financial intermediaries is necessary to expand participation.

FIGURE 4 | Key developments and allocation of Green Sukuk in Indonesia (Data Source: Primambudi 2023; Teichmann et al. 2023) (illustrated by authors).

In summary, low corporate involvement and insufficient private-investment integration are the two main barriers to scaling Indonesia's Green Sukuk market. Overcoming these constraints through targeted incentives, investor confidence-building, and regulatory clarity will be essential for broader adoption across ASEAN. Indonesia's Green Sukuk success has far-reaching implications for ASEAN, particularly for nations with strong Islamic finance sectors such as Malaysia, Brunei, and parts of Thailand and the Philippines. This financing model can help ASEAN scale sustainable investments through Sharia-compliant financial mechanisms. Table 4 outlines how Indonesia's Green Sukuk serves as a blueprint for other ASEAN markets.

Table 4 highlights how Indonesia's Green Sukuk framework can enhance ASEAN's sustainable finance ecosystem by integrating Islamic finance with climate investment strategies. Countries such as Malaysia and Brunei already have established Islamic finance industries, making them ideal candidates for replicating Indonesia's model. Additionally, sovereign Green Sukuk issuance provides a structured pathway for other ASEAN markets to develop climate-aligned financing instruments that align with global green finance standards. By successfully mobilizing capital for green projects, Indonesia provides a clear and replicable model for ASEAN nations seeking to enhance their climate finance strategies. With strong investor interest, progressive government policies, and strategic institutional support, Indonesia is well-positioned to lead ASEAN's green finance transition and inspire broader adoption of sustainable Islamic finance instrument (Hidayat et al. 2024; Zuhroh and Malik 2023).

4.2 | Singapore: Carbon Tax and the Development of a Carbon Trading Hub

Singapore's carbon tax and its evolution into a carbon trading hub reflect a significant commitment toward environmental sustainability and regulatory innovation. The carbon tax, implemented in 2019, was notable as it represented Asia's first

TABLE 4 | Relevance of Indonesia's Green Sukuk to ASEAN.

Key area	Relevance to ASEAN	Impact on ASEAN
Islamic finance for sustainability (Primambudi 2023; Teichmann et al. 2023)	Green Sukuk demonstrates how Islamic finance can drive sustainability and climate finance goals.	Strengthens ASEAN's green finance ecosystem through Sharia-compliant investment models.
Blueprint for sovereign green bonds (Fitrah and Soemitra 2022; Ministry of Finance 2024)	Indonesia's model sets a precedent for ASEAN emerging markets interested in sovereign green bond issuance.	Provides a replicable framework for nations seeking climate-aligned financing strategies.
Expanding ASEAN's Islamic green finance market (Kusmayadi and Koestoer 2022; Sapiri and Putra 2023)	Countries with strong Islamic finance sectors (e.g., Malaysia, Brunei) can replicate the Green Sukuk model.	Enhances regional cooperation in sustainable finance and cross-border green investment.

successful nationwide carbon tax initiative, establishing a regulatory framework aimed at mitigating greenhouse gas emissions (Secretariat 2025).

Figure 5 shows the carbon tax trajectory between 2019 and 2030 according to the National Climate Change Secretariat (2025).

FIGURE 5 | Singapore's carbon tax trajectory (2019–2030) (Data Source: Secretariat 2025).

Singapore launched the region's first carbon pricing scheme in early 2019, starting at S\$5 per tonne of CO₂ equivalent for the initial 5 years. As part of its climate strategy, this rate was increased to S\$25 in 2024, with further hikes planned to reach up to S\$80 per tonne by 2030.

To complement its carbon tax, Singapore is actively positioning itself as a regional carbon trading hub, leveraging its strong financial sector and regulatory infrastructure to facilitate cross-border carbon credit trading under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (Singapore Economic Development Board 2025). Research highlights that combining carbon taxes with emissions trading mitigates economic burdens associated with standalone carbon taxes. Zou et al. (2020) emphasize that a dual approach of taxation and trading can balance economic growth with environmental objectives, reducing negative market impacts (Zou et al. 2020). Similarly, Liu et al. (2023) argue that integrating policy instruments enhances effectiveness, ensuring that carbon pricing mechanisms do not stifle business competitiveness (Liu et al. 2023).

Singapore's regulatory environment and financial infrastructure make it an attractive location for carbon trading investments, facilitating the development of market mechanisms that enhance carbon pricing efficiency. A well-structured carbon pricing system is expected to accelerate the adoption of low-carbon technologies while encouraging private-sector participation in emissions reduction efforts (Liu et al. 2023). The effectiveness of Singapore's carbon tax in shaping sustainable economic behavior can be analyzed through Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, which assess trade-offs between environmental policies and economic growth (Li and Peng 2020; Nguyễn 2023). Studies indicate that:

- Properly implemented carbon taxation can yield significant environmental benefits without imposing severe economic burdens on households and businesses.
- Singapore's carbon pricing policy ensures a gradual increase, allowing industries time to adapt while incentivizing cleaner technologies.

To help businesses offset their emissions, Singapore launched Climate Impact X (CIX) with SGX, DBS, Standard Chartered, and Temasek to let firms buy high-integrity offsets, and from 2024 companies may use eligible credits for up to 5% of taxable emissions; Singapore also signed Article 6 bilateral offset agreements, including with Papua New Guinea (Quah and Tan 2022). However, key challenges remain: safeguarding economic competitiveness, ensuring carbon-credit integrity, and improving regional policy alignment to limit leakage. Table 5 summarizes the main barriers affecting Singapore's carbon pricing strategy.

As highlighted in Table 5, the most pressing challenge is balancing economic competitiveness. Industries with high carbon emissions face rising costs, which could affect foreign investment attractiveness. Another key issue is carbon credit integrity, where ensuring the credibility of voluntary carbon offsets remains critical to prevent greenwashing. Lastly, regional coordination remains a concern, as varying carbon pricing mechanisms across ASEAN increase regulatory uncertainty, delaying the potential for a harmonized emissions trading system.

Singapore's experience with carbon pricing offers valuable insights for ASEAN countries that are still in the early stages of implementing carbon taxation and emissions trading systems (ETS). By positioning itself as a regional carbon trading hub, Singapore sets an example for market-driven carbon finance solutions. The key lessons that ASEAN countries can draw from Singapore's carbon pricing framework are:

- *Leadership and precedent* (Secretariat 2025; Singapore Economic Development Board 2025): Singapore's carbon tax, the first in ASEAN, provides a practical benchmark other country can adapt when introducing carbon taxation and piloting ETS.
- *Market infrastructure and regional liquidity* (Liu et al. 2023; Singapore Economic Development Board 2025): Building a trading hub and supporting cross-border credit exchanges can attract institutional investors and deepen the region's green-finance ecosystem.

TABLE 5 | Challenges in Singapore's carbon pricing strategy.

Challenge	Key issue	Impact
Balancing economic competitiveness (Zou et al. 2020)	Rising carbon tax increases operational costs for energy-intensive industries.	Raises concerns about business competitiveness and foreign investment attractiveness.
Carbon credit integrity (Liu et al. 2023)	Need for high-quality, verifiable carbon credits in voluntary markets.	Prevents greenwashing and ensures market credibility.
Regional coordination (Quah and Tan 2022)	Aligning carbon pricing policies with ASEAN counterparts.	Avoids carbon leakage and promotes a harmonized regional emissions trading system.

- *Structured pathway to net zero* (Liu et al. 2023; Quah and Tan 2022): A gradual and transparent carbon-price trajectory, combined with credible MRV and trading, helps firms adjust while maintaining environmental ambition.

Taken together, Singapore's model shows that integrating carbon taxation with market trading can balance economic stability and environmental ambition. Therefore, ASEAN countries can adapt three elements: clear price signals, credible market infrastructure with robust MRV, and a gradual trajectory that lets firms adjust while investment scales.

4.3 | Thailand: Thailand Voluntary Emission Reduction Program (T-VER)

Thailand has actively implemented voluntary carbon pricing mechanisms as part of its strategy to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 and net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2065 (Organization (TGO) et al. 2024). T-VER was developed as an alternative to the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), addressing its high costs, technical complexity, and verification challenges. The program aims to increase participation in voluntary emission reduction projects, particularly for small and medium-sized project developers, by simplifying registration, verification, and certification processes (Organization (TGO) et al. 2024).

Figure 6 illustrates the key features of Thailand's Voluntary Emission Reduction Program (T-VER), focusing on project scope, credit utilization, market expansion, and the Premium T-VER initiative. This framework plays a crucial role in Thailand's climate strategy, fostering voluntary carbon market development and enabling businesses and organizations to participate in carbon offsetting initiatives. The government has reinforced T-VER's regulatory framework, linking it to national carbon pricing policies such as the Carbon Credit Management Guideline and Mechanism (CCMGM)

FIGURE 6 | Key features of T-VER (Data Source: Organization (TGO) et al. 2024).

and the forthcoming Climate Change Act (2026), which will introduce mandatory ETS, carbon tax, and credit regulations. Additionally, Thailand is exploring Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs) under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement to align its voluntary carbon market with international standards (Creagy et al. 2024).

Table 6 summarizes the major obstacles facing Thailand's voluntary carbon market. As seen in Table, one of the most pressing issues is the oversupply of T-VER credits, which, coupled with low market demand, reduces liquidity and price stability. Additionally, Thailand's voluntary credits lack international recognition, limiting their attractiveness to global investors who prefer Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) or Gold Standard (GS) credits. Regulatory uncertainty and weak verification processes further delay credit issuance, discouraging new project developers. By addressing these challenges, Thailand can strengthen its voluntary carbon market, attract international investors, and drive a more sustainable climate strategy.

The T-VER scheme, with its project-based crediting and sectoral flexibility, also offers a foundation for future alignment with regional mechanisms such as the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), enabling Thailand to prepare for carbon accounting integration in international trade contexts. Table 7 highlights the relevance of T-VER to ASEAN. Thailand's Voluntary Emission Reduction Program (T-VER) plays a pivotal role in shaping ASEAN's carbon market policies, renewable energy goals, and climate adaptation strategies. It provides a scalable model for voluntary carbon markets, supporting cross-border trading, sustainable land-use practices, and green finance mechanisms. T-VER aligns with ASEAN's climate commitments under the Paris Agreement, promoting carbon pricing frameworks, emissions trading systems (ETS), and private-sector participation in sustainability efforts. The integration of forestry-based carbon sequestration, biochar projects, and digital carbon trading platforms strengthens ASEAN's climate resilience and economic sustainability.

By expanding T-VER's methodologies, ASEAN can harmonize carbon market regulations, facilitate investment in clean energy,

TABLE 6 | Summary of key challenges in T-VER.

Challenge	Key issue	Impact	References
Oversupply of T-VER credits	Too many carbon credits, low market demand	Carbon credits remain unsold, reducing liquidity	(Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Lack of international recognition	Limited alignment with global standards (ICVCM, Article 6)	Investors prefer other carbon credits (VCS, Gold Standard)	(Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Weak verification & transparency	Slow, costly credit verification processes	Delays in credit issuance, discouraging new projects	(Creagy et al. 2024)
Community-based carbon market barriers	Limited incentives for forestry projects	Unequal benefit-sharing discourages participation	(Chaiya 2025)
Agricultural carbon credit challenges	Unclear financial incentives for biochar & biomass	Farmers stick to traditional practices instead of adopting carbon reduction	(Kanchanapiya and Tantisattayakul 2025)
Uncertain policy & carbon pricing regulations	Thailand's Climate Change Act is still under development	Businesses delay investment in voluntary carbon credits	(Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)

and develop a unified carbon pricing framework. This will drive ASEAN's transition toward net-zero emissions by 2050, reinforcing its position in the global carbon market.

5 | Discussion and Policy Recommendations

This section synthesizes findings from the preceding analyses and case studies to identify practical strategies for scaling green finance and carbon market development in ASEAN. In this review, green finance and carbon market mechanisms are emphasized as the central pillars of ASEAN's low-carbon transition, while related domains such as digital tools, regional power trading, and sustainability standards are treated as supporting enablers that enhance transparency, market integration, and policy implementation. We assume that policy transfer depends on political commitment, institutional capacity for MRV and enforcement, market depth and liquidity, grid readiness and interconnection, and fiscal space for transitional support; where these conditions are weak, elements from non-ASEAN models require adaptation rather than direct adoption.

5.1 | Comparative Analysis of Global Carbon Markets and Green Finance Strategies

This section examines international best practices in green finance and carbon market policy, identifying tools that ASEAN can adapt to advance its low-carbon transition. Lessons are drawn from leading systems in the EU, China, the US, and Southeast Asia, with emphasis on both proven instruments and cautionary insights.

Several global models offer valuable insights for ASEAN's transition. Table 8 compares regulatory, market-based, and digital tools across the EU, the United States, China, India, Brazil, and Singapore, including CBAM, carbon pricing, green bond standards, renewable energy auctions, blockchain applications, and AI tools for carbon tracking. While these practices

are informative, ASEAN's political economy presents both opportunities and constraints. Governance structures, levels of development, and energy policy priorities vary across member states. Countries such as Singapore and Malaysia have more advanced regulatory environments and financial ecosystems that are conducive to green finance, whereas emerging economies such as Laos, Cambodia, and Myanmar face constraints in institutional capacity, investment readiness, and regulatory enforcement.

Regional diversity is also evident in energy profiles. Indonesia and Vietnam remain more coal-reliant, while the Philippines and Thailand are increasing renewable investment. Governance approaches range from centralized models to decentralized systems, which influence the speed and consistency of policy implementation. Political will, regulatory transparency, and institutional strength will determine the success of carbon market integration and green finance scaling.

Therefore, ASEAN should localize global models through flexible frameworks, targeted capacity building, and differentiated timelines. A sequenced approach that begins with pilots and early MRV, followed by price setting, market integration, and digital transparency, can align instruments with country conditions and improve the likelihood of durable outcomes.

5.2 | Lessons From ASEAN Case Studies

The case studies of Indonesia, Singapore, and Thailand highlight key strategies, challenges, and opportunities for scaling green finance and carbon market development across ASEAN. Each country has implemented different mechanisms, providing valuable insights for regional cooperation, policy harmonization, and investment mobilization. The following table summarizes key strategies and the lessons learned from these case studies, offering a comparative perspective on green finance initiatives in ASEAN.

TABLE 7 | Relevance of T-VER to ASEAN.

Key area	Relevance to ASEAN	Impact on ASEAN	References
Alignment with ASEAN carbon market development	T-VER serves as a regional model for voluntary carbon markets and supports cross-border carbon trading	Harmonizes carbon market regulations and strengthens regional cooperation in carbon credit trading	(Creagy et al. 2024; Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Contribution to ASEAN's renewable energy transition	Supports ASEAN's 23% renewable energy goal by 2025, especially in solar, wind, and biomass projects	Facilitates private-sector investment in renewable energy and encourages cross-border clean energy financing	(Creagy et al. 2024; Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Strengthening ASEAN's climate policy & carbon pricing	ASEAN is developing carbon pricing and ETS mechanisms, and T-VER serves as a pilot program	Encourages policy innovation and strengthens carbon market transparency in ASEAN	(Creagy et al. 2024; Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Advancing sustainable agriculture & forestry	Promotes biochar and forestry-based sequestration, critical for agriculture-reliant ASEAN economies	Provides a replicable model for integrating agriculture into carbon markets and supporting community-led forestry	(Chaiya 2025; Kanchanapiya and Tantisattayakul 2025)
Addressing climate vulnerability & resilience	T-VER's community-based projects enhance climate adaptation strategies across ASEAN	Strengthens ASEAN's climate resilience framework through voluntary carbon markets	(Chaiya 2025; Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)
Promoting private sector engagement in green finance	T-VER aligns with ASEAN's Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, promoting corporate carbon neutrality	Enhances private sector investment in voluntary carbon markets	(Creagy et al. 2024; Organization (TGO) et al. 2024)

Table 9 provides a comparative overview of key strategies and lessons derived from Indonesia, Singapore, and Thailand in advancing green finance and carbon market development within ASEAN. Indonesia demonstrates how sovereign green sukuk can anchor investor confidence and crowd in private issuance. Meanwhile, Singapore shows that carbon pricing and market infrastructure can guide corporate abatement and attract liquidity. Furthermore, Thailand's finance roadmap, taxonomy, voluntary market, and floating solar indicate how policy clarity and technology choices can accelerate deployment. While these international experiences offer critical insights, ASEAN's pathway must account for its unique political, economic, and institutional dynamics. Building on these global lessons, the next section presents targeted policy recommendations tailored to the ASEAN context.

To facilitate ASEAN's sustainable energy transition, the policy recommendations outlined below are structured into clear

strategic phases: short-term actions (1–2 years) for immediate impact, and long-term strategies (5+ years) to sustain regional integration and capacity-building. This phased approach provides policymakers and stakeholders with a practical and strategic vision to systematically enhance green finance and carbon markets.

5.3 | Roadmap: Short- and Long-Term Recommendations

Table 10 summarizes immediate, actionable steps that ASEAN policymakers should prioritize. Short-term steps focus on foundational rules, pilot markets, early investments, and digital trials. Long-term actions build on these foundations to achieve regional integration, scale finance, and modernize energy systems.

TABLE 8 | Insights for ASEAN from global best practice.

Policy area	Global best practice	Country/region	Insights for ASEAN
Green bond market development	EU Green Bond Standard (EU GBS) ensures transparency and credibility for investors.	EU (Fatica and Panzica 2020)	ASEAN can develop a harmonized green bond standard to attract sustainable finance.
Carbon pricing & trading	EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) effectively reduced emissions via a cap-and-trade system.	EU (Sitarz et al. 2024)	ASEAN could establish a regional carbon trading system, starting with sectoral pilots in power and industry.
Carbon border adjustment	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) prevents carbon leakage and incentivizes clean production.	EU (Perdana and Vielle 2022)	ASEAN could explore a regional CBAM to encourage cleaner production and trade alignment.
Renewable energy auctions	Reverse auctions significantly reduced solar and wind power costs.	India, Brazil (Aleluia et al. 2022)	ASEAN governments can adopt auction-based procurement for cost-effective renewable energy deployment.
Tax incentives for renewables	Investment tax credits (ITC) and Inflation Reduction Act (IRA).	US (Zhao et al. 2023; Bistline et al. 2023)	ASEAN can introduce targeted tax incentives for renewable energy developers and investors.
Blended finance for green energy	Public-private green finance mechanisms de-risk investments.	World Bank, ADB (ADB 2022)	ASEAN can develop blended finance programs to scale renewable projects with institutional support.
Grid modernization for renewables	Smart grids and energy storage incentives improved renewable energy integration.	Germany, China (Agency (IEA) 2023)	ASEAN nations should invest in grid modernization to support large-scale solar and wind deployment.
Carbon credit market development	National carbon credit markets linked with global voluntary schemes.	Singapore, South Korea (Rakhiemah et al. 2024)	ASEAN countries should standardize carbon credit markets and integrate them with international mechanisms.
Blockchain for green finance	Blockchain and smart contracts used to tokenize green bonds and track carbon credits (e.g., Project Genesis, Climate Impact X).	Hong Kong, Singapore, Global (Boumaiza and Maher 2024; Mallesons 2021)	ASEAN can adopt blockchain platforms for carbon trading to improve transparency, reduce transaction costs (by up to 60%), and enhance traceability and MRV systems (Boumaiza and Maher 2024).
AI for green finance and emission reduction	AI-driven models (e.g., FMFG, simulation-based optimization) enhance ESG analysis and CO ₂ reduction efficiency in industrial sectors.	India, Pakistan (Hemanand et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2025)	ASEAN can apply AI to strengthen green finance strategies, improve ESG scoring, and optimize policies for industrial decarbonization and investment efficiency.

TABLE 9 | Lessons from ASEAN's green finance and carbon market development.

Country	Key strategy	Lessons	Potential for implementation
Indonesia	Green Sukuk & Islamic finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – First sovereign Green Sukuk model in the world. – Demonstrates Islamic finance's role in sustainable investments. – Encourages more sovereign and corporate green bond issuances. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Replicable model for Malaysia, Brunei, and other Islamic finance markets. – Can be expanded to corporate Sukuk issuance in ASEAN.
Singapore	Carbon pricing & trading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – First ASEAN country to implement a carbon tax. – Developing a regional carbon trading hub. – Highlights the importance of strong regulatory frameworks for emissions trading. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ASEAN-wide carbon pricing cooperation can align carbon tax rates. – Singapore's carbon market can facilitate cross-border trading under Article 6.
Thailand	Green finance & renewable energy expansion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Launched a sustainable finance roadmap & green taxonomy. – Developing a voluntary carbon market. – Pioneering floating solar projects as an emerging trend. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ASEAN-wide standardized green taxonomies. – Floating solar can be scaled across Southeast Asia's hydropower reservoirs.

TABLE 10 | Integrated short- and long-term policy recommendations for ASEAN.

Priority area	Short-term actions (1–2 years)	Long-term strategic actions (5+ years)
Harmonizing green finance standards	Develop ASEAN-wide green bond guidance aligned with EU GBS and ACMF. Expand green sukuk.	Institutionalize harmonized taxonomies and disclosure frameworks across ASEAN.
Carbon market development	Launch sector-specific trading pilots in power and industry. Build early MRV rules and registries.	Transition to a regionally integrated ASEAN ETS and establish a market stability reserve.
Carbon pricing and trade (CBAM)	Introduce carbon-pricing pilots and baseline MRV for major emitters.	Harmonize carbon-price trajectories and assess a regional CBAM aligned with trade rules.
Renewable energy incentives	Run competitive renewable auctions modeled on proven designs.	Scale deployment via regional grid links and smart-grid investments.
Mobilizing sustainable investment	Use blended finance and green bonds to crowd in early private capital.	Expand public–private partnerships and institutionalize blended finance platforms.
Digital innovations	Pilot blockchain registries for credit tracking and apply AI for ESG analytics.	Deploy full-scale digital MRV and AI-driven investment and policy tools.
Capacity building and cooperation	Deliver ASEAN-wide training on green finance, carbon markets, and digital MRV.	Strengthen regional governance for markets, standards, and cross-border coordination.

Building on the discussion above, Table 10 sets out the recommended actions, grouped by priority area and implementation horizon. In the near term, quick wins should build momentum, strengthen investor confidence, and develop institutional capacity. Early steps such as piloting carbon markets, aligning

green finance standards, and conducting targeted training can demonstrate progress while laying the groundwork for broader reforms. Over the medium to long term, the focus should shift toward integrating regional carbon markets, harmonizing carbon pricing, and expanding renewable energy through cross-border

TABLE 11 | Risk area, description of risk, and mitigation strategy.

Risk area	Description of risk	Mitigation strategy
Fragmentation of carbon markets	Diverse national regulations could create fragmented carbon trading systems.	Develop a regional governance framework and shared MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, Verification) protocols to harmonize efforts.
Governance and corruption risks	Weak institutional capacities could undermine trust and credibility in carbon markets and green finance mechanisms.	Strengthen transparency through digital MRV platforms and establish robust compliance and enforcement systems.
Economic competitiveness risks	Carbon pricing may impact the competitiveness of emerging ASEAN economies and industries.	Implement phased carbon pricing with transitional support for vulnerable sectors and SMEs.
Technology and infrastructure gaps	Uneven digital infrastructure could limit blockchain and AI adoption for green finance tracking.	Prioritize regional investments in digital infrastructure and capacity-building programs.
Compliance risks with global markets	Failure to align carbon pricing and green finance standards could hinder ASEAN's global trade competitiveness.	Align ASEAN frameworks with evolving global standards (e.g., EU CBAM, ISO MRV standards) and engage in proactive trade diplomacy.

grid modernization, which together enable scale, resilience, and competitiveness. Throughout both phases, digital systems and regional cooperation act as cross-cutting enablers by improving transparency, reducing transaction costs, and supporting credible monitoring, reporting, and verification.

5.4 | Identified Risks and Strategic Mitigation Measures

Table 11 outlines the principal risks that ASEAN may encounter when implementing green finance and carbon market initiatives, along with corresponding mitigation strategies to ensure long-term success.

Identifying and proactively addressing risks is essential to safeguarding ASEAN's transition efforts. Harmonization of carbon markets, strengthening institutional governance, and enhancing digital infrastructure are critical risk-mitigation pillars. Strategic risk management will not only build credibility but also attract sustained investment and international cooperation.

5.5 | Social and Distributional Implications

A fair energy transition in ASEAN needs to consider who pays the costs, who gains the benefits, and who may be left behind. If these issues are ignored, higher energy prices and major economic changes could increase inequality and reduce public support for clean energy policies (International Energy Agency 2024). Therefore, policy design should link pricing and finance reforms with protections for households, workers, and firms while improving access and opportunity (ACMF

and ADB 2024; ASEAN Centre for Energy 2025; International Labour Organization 2024). Specifically:

- *Affordability and access*: pair carbon-pricing or subsidy reforms with lifeline tariffs, targeted rebates, and support for clean cooking, efficiency, and distributed renewables in low-income and rural areas (ASEAN Centre for Energy 2025; International Energy Agency 2024).
- *Jobs and skills*: fund reskilling, job-matching, and local content programs in regions affected by fuel switching and plant retirements, ensuring workers can move into growing clean-energy roles (ASEAN Centre for Energy 2025; International Labour Organization 2024).
- *Competitiveness*: provide time-bound, declining assistance for energy-intensive, trade-exposed sectors, linked to credible decarbonization plans and robust MRV, to limit leakage while preserving incentives (World Bank 2025).
- *Public acceptance*: recycle part of carbon-pricing revenues to households and SMEs and report transparently on beneficiaries, because visible benefits increase trust and durability (International Labour Organization 2024; World Bank 2025).
- *Fair use of finance*: direct portions of green-bond proceeds and ETS or carbon-tax revenues to social protection, skills funds, and community-scale energy access, as encouraged under the ASEAN Transition Finance Guidance, which promotes inclusive and accountable transition-finance practices (ACMF and ADB 2024; International Labour Organization 2024).

Taken together, these measures align green finance and carbon markets with just-transition principles, improving affordability, employment, and legitimacy while increasing the political durability of ASEAN's low-carbon pathway.

5.6 | Limitations and Future Research Directions

While this study provides a comparative analysis of global best practices and tailored policy recommendations for ASEAN, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The analysis primarily focuses on regulatory frameworks, financial instruments, and digital innovations, with less emphasis on the detailed socioeconomic impacts across diverse ASEAN member states. Future research could explore the distributional effects of carbon pricing mechanisms on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), informal sectors, and vulnerable communities. Additionally, empirical studies on operationalizing regional carbon pricing coordination and digital MRV implementation across politically and economically diverse ASEAN countries would strengthen the practical application of the proposed strategies.

Building on these findings, the concluding section summarizes key insights and outlines future research directions for ASEAN's sustainable energy transition.

6 | Conclusion

The ASEAN region faces significant challenges in its transition to a sustainable, low-carbon energy future, including high dependence on fossil fuels, fragmented policy frameworks, and insufficient financial mechanisms for clean energy investments. However, green finance instruments such as green bonds, carbon pricing, and emissions trading systems (ETS) can play a transformative role in accelerating the region's energy transition. Drawing from global best practices, this study has explored how ASEAN can leverage harmonized financial frameworks, market-based carbon pricing strategies, and digital innovations to mobilize investments and enhance energy security.

This study examined how elements of the EU ETS, EU Green Bond Standard, and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism could inform ASEAN approaches. While ASEAN has made notable progress in green finance led by Indonesia's Green Sukuk, Singapore's carbon tax, and Malaysia's sustainability-linked bonds, the region's carbon market remains highly fragmented, with varying levels of policy maturity and investor confidence. Singapore leads with an established carbon tax and trading framework, while Indonesia and Malaysia have pioneered voluntary carbon markets. Other nations, such as Vietnam and Thailand, are in the early stages of implementing carbon pricing policies, whereas Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar remain at the preliminary development phase, relying primarily on donor-funded renewable energy projects. To effectively bridge its energy gap and scale up green finance and carbon markets, ASEAN must pursue a harmonized, integrated regional strategy that includes:

- **Strengthening Regulatory Frameworks**—Establishing standardized ASEAN-wide guidelines for green bonds, carbon trading, and emissions reductions to ensure cross-border investment compatibility and policy alignment.
- **Expanding Green Finance Instruments**—Promoting sustainability-linked bonds, carbon offset markets, blended

finance, and Islamic Green Sukuk to attract diverse investors and de-risk clean energy projects.

- **Developing an ASEAN-Wide Carbon Market**—Building on the EU ETS model, ASEAN should link national carbon pricing mechanisms to create a regional emission trading hub, enhancing market liquidity and price stability.
- **Enhancing Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**—Strengthening government incentives, tax benefits, and risk-sharing mechanisms to encourage private-sector participation in clean energy investment.
- **Leveraging Digital and AI-Driven Solutions**—Integrating blockchain-based carbon credit trading, AI-driven investment analytics, and digital monitoring tools to improve transparency, efficiency, and investor confidence in ASEAN's green finance markets.

Successful implementation depends on political commitment, institutional capacity for MRV and enforcement, market depth and grid readiness, and fiscal space for transitional support. Sequencing is essential: pilots and early MRV should precede price setting, market linkage, and wider digital deployment. Regional platforms such as the ASEAN Centre for Energy and the ASEAN Capital Markets Forum can facilitate coordination and standard setting. Social and distributional measures, including revenue recycling, skills programs, and targeted affordability support, will strengthen public acceptance and policy durability.

By adapting global lessons to regional realities, ASEAN can scale green finance, integrate carbon markets, and mobilize investment for renewable infrastructure. Timely and coordinated action can improve energy security, attract climate finance, and advance a just and inclusive low-carbon transition. This review contributes to the literature on regional carbon market integration and sustainable finance in developing economies.

Author Contributions

Ohn Zin Lin: conceptualization (lead), formal analysis (lead), writing – original draft (lead), writing – review and editing (lead). **Dagmar Juchelkova:** funding acquisition (lead), project administration (lead), supervision (lead). **Libor Štěpanec:** formal analysis (lead), validation (lead), visualization (supporting). **Hnin Yee Aye:** formal analysis (equal), investigation (equal), resources (supporting), visualization (equal). **Kharisma Bani Adam:** data curation (supporting), formal analysis (supporting), resources (supporting), validation (supporting).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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